

DESIGN OF HEMATOLOGICAL ELECTROPHORESIS MACHINE.

A PROJECT REPORT

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BONAFIDE CERTIFICATE

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DECLARATION

We hereby declare that the project report entitled “DESIGN OF HEMATOLOGICAL ELECTROPHORESIS DEVICE” submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirement for the Bachelor degree in ENGINEERING BIOMEDICAL under the supervision of Mr. SAMPSON AMPONSAH in the department of Biomedical Engineering at All Nations University, Koforidua is a record of a bonafide project work conducted between May 2017 to May 2021. We further declare that the work recorded in this project has never been submitted in part or in whole, for any other degree, award or examination whatsoever at this of any other university’

DEDICATION

This work is dedicated to God Almighty for his grace. It is also dedicated to our beloved Parents, friends, Siblings for their immense support.

The project is dedicated to our all our lecturers, who taught and inculcated in us the skill and the expertise to make this project a success. We were inspired by their guidance, dedication and critique, which encouraged us through the project.

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ABSTRACT

Society is burdened with vast of problems but issue of genetic and blood related health conditions has been subjected to mythical beliefs. The objective of this project is to design and implement a low-cost hematological electrophoresis machine that will help people to understand the concept of gene compatibility and help diagnose genetic related issues. The system is based on electrophoresis that's the passing of electricity through blood proteins to separate them. When blood samples are taken and run by the machine the DNA and blood fragments are separated and determined. With the help of the machine blood protein are been able to count which plays important roles in genetic health disorder diagnosing.

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CHAPTER 1

1.0 Background on The Study

The use of electrophoresis to separate nucleic acids began in the early 1960s. At the time, nucleic acids were commonly fractionated by density gradient centrifugation based on sedimentation velocities, which are determined by size and conformation of the nucleic acids. Density gradient centrifugation took considerable amounts of time, required heavy equipment, and needed high inputs of samples. For alternatives, researchers began to explore characteristics of DNA mobility in ionic, or electrolytic, solutions when an electrical field was applied a process termed electrophoresis. Within a few years, nucleic acid electrophoresis evolved into utilizing a gel matrix as a separation medium, borrowing the technique already employed in protein electrophoresis. Agar (a naturally derived carbohydrate), agarose (a component of agar), polyacrylamide (a synthetic gel), and agarose-acrylamide composite gels were found to be successful as matrices for hematology, blood proteins, DNA and RNA electrophoresis, in the mid- to late 1960s. Cellulose acetate electrophoresis is a type of zone electrophoresis that separates molecules in liquid form such as proteins on a membrane or stripe made of cellulose acetate. Developed by a German chemist, Joachim Kohn (1912-1987) in 1957, cellulose acetate electrophoresis was the second form of zone electrophoresis, after filter paper electrophoresis. It was also one of the earliest electrophoretic techniques adopted in clinical laboratories for routine diagnosis that is still in use to date (**Rocco, 2005**). In cellulose acetate electrophoresis, a membrane or stripe made of cellulose acetate is used as a support matrix to separate components in the sample. As with typical zone electrophoresis, electrophoretic separation occurs in a homogeneous buffer system. The support matrix or medium is submerged in an electrophoresis running buffer maintained at a definite pH value, and electrophoretic separation is conducted for a definite time (**Westermeier et al., 2005**). It can provide a molecular sieving effect on electrophoretic separation of the sample, based on the size of the pores between the molecules of the support matrix. It can also reduce convection currents that are generated from excessive heat, which occurs during electrophoresis. When the separation is completed, components of the sample are isolated into distinct bands or zones. Each band represents constituents in the samples that possess similar or identical characteristics (**Jorgenson, 1986; Walker, 2010**).

In the case of cellulose acetate electrophoresis, membranes in the form of sheets or stripes made from cellulose acetate are saturated with the running buffer. Each end of the buffer-saturated stripes

overlaps with a filter paper wick that reaches into the buffer in an electrophoresis tank. Samples of interest are dotted onto the surface at about half or one-third of the length of the cellulose acetate membrane (Kohn, 1969; Walker, 2010). The separation begins when an electric current is applied to each end of the stripe, which acts as an anode and cathode. At the end of the electrophoresis, separated components can be stained and unstained for visualization purposes and for further quantitative analyses. Cellulose acetate electrophoresis is suitable for rapid screening purposes by comparing the pattern of separation obtained from the sample of interest with that of a known reference. The technique is applicable to various types of samples, such as nucleic acids, proteins, polypeptides dyes and mixtures of dyes and polysaccharides (Kohn, 1962; Dudman & Bishop, 1968).

The aim of this project is to develop a simple system for the teaching, demonstration, and practical use of a gel electrophoresis in hematology with low cost. The intent of this study was to systematically reevaluate the use of each component in agarose gel electrophoresis and to assess available substitutes for compatibility and practicality, to provide a comprehensive tool kit of materials for educators to build their own teaching simulations of hematological gel electrophoresis.

Today's fast changing environment is causing direct effect on health care and available equipment, as such flexible and competent equipment with equal or better performance are readily accepted. Electrophoresis of hemoglobin through gels of agarose or polyacrylamide (PA) has been one of the most widely used techniques of molecular biology during the past decade, serving both analytical and preparative purposes. The molecular theory of this process has been developing slowly over the same period as the result of the efforts of a small but expanding group of people. Hence the high demand of the equipment. These are direct substitutes to heavy, bulky, and expensive equipment for blood protein tests.

Cellulose acetate accounts for one of the earliest support matrices used for zone electrophoresis. Since its conception, there are newer forms of zone electrophoresis that offer higher resolving power without compromising separation time or results. Techniques such as gel and capillary electrophoresis have mostly replaced cellulose acetate electrophoresis in most research laboratories. Nevertheless, cellulose acetate electrophoresis still retains its place in routine clinical diagnosis due to its ease of use and adaptability

The study would make use of both primary and secondary source of data to analyze the information. The primary data is the type of data collected from the field not for any other purpose to one side of the study at hand. The tool use for collecting the data consists of questionnaires, observation and interview.

The secondary data is a type of data that already exist and it is however easy to be collected. It includes magazines, journals, past student project work, and other purchasing supply books from the library.

Overall, gel electrophoresis has become a universal technique in molecular biology for separating blood proteins and nucleic acids. Not only is this analytical and preparative method integral to common workflows like molecular cloning and PCR, but it also plays an important role for nucleic acid separation and analysis in emerging technologies like genome editing and next-generation sequencing. The significance of this study would help the student to be acquainted to the use of electrophoresis device. It will help the healthcare facility to attend to more people in a minimum time while this reduces pressure on components. The study would serve as a point reference for student and corporate healthcare organization who may conduct further research in the area of study, as it would address some engineering issues.

1.1 Problem statement

Most of genetic, natural, and other forms of medical predicaments have been laid down to mythical beliefs in our society. For instance, incompatible parents giving forth to offerings with dysfunctional genetical orders were subject down do wrong doings to the gods. Other genetic disorder due to blood protein composition which aren't well understood are being interpreted differently. This brings to the need for hematological device for measuring and reading blood protein.

1.2 Aim

To design a cost-effective hematological electrophoresis device

1.3 Objectives

To achieve the aim at the end of this project, the following key objectives shall be undertaken with keen interest.

1. To make use of chargeable batteries to reduce over dependence on electricity.
2. To make use of ceramic casing to improve insulation to reduce cost.
3. To make use of LED lights and adjustable controls to improve portability.

1.4 JUSTIFICATION

The hematological electrophoresis device is a cost effective and reliable. It increases awareness of the various blood disorders and genetic dysfunction which has nothing to do with voodoo and witchcraft. The portability and use of chargeable batteries will make the device available in urban and rural areas of a developing country.

CHAPTER 2

2.0 literature Review

The available literature on the acetate gel electrophoresis is presented in detail in this chapter. It gives an idea about the current situation in terms of what has been done and suggestions on what needs to be done to increase the knowledge and understanding of the problem.

2.1 Related Works

Osterman et al. (1984), conducted a project on the migration safety of the protein and nucleic acids as their shape size and components are the basic needs of the process. They recommended the use of buffers such Tris buffer to aid in moving charged particles and a application of electrical current.

Wiltfang et al (1991) conducted a project on the size weight and mass of proteins to be taken at a particular cycle. They succeeded to up to about 100hg which is quite good enough using new multiphasic buffer system for sodium dodecyl sulfate-polyacrylamide gel

Westermeier, (2005) conducted a project on availability of different mediums to be exploited. They based their search on pore size and network density of polyacrylamide gels, which are dependent absolutely on the content of acrylamide monomers and the proportion of bisacrylamide coss-linkers in the gel matrixes, can be regulated in a wide scale by controlling the concentration of acrylamide monomers in the gels and the ratio of bisacrylamide cross-linkers to the acrylamide monomers.

2.2 Need for Project

Major significant changes in the electrophoresis have been based on the gel matrix as greater mass proteins are being processed at a time. The western community focus the project on technology

enhancement not to say that wasn't considered in our project. We believe in step-by-step achievement and hence the need to tackle our power dependent problems. The SelVet 24 is the semi-automated analyzer for electrophoresis on cellulose acetate capable of processing up to 24 samples per single operating cycle. The reagents are manually loaded on board by the operator before starting the operating cycle and removed at the end of the working session. In this way the SelVet 24 offers an excellent compromise between the cost of the analyzer and the services offered but just too much expensive.

The MicroPhor is a densitometric reader for electrophoresis membranes both in Agarose gel and in cellulose acetate (supported and not supported). Small and simple to use like all our analyzers

In our part of the world where alternate source power is limited and create problems. Our project seeks to be less dependent on power. The portability of the machine is a great factor as it will be easily and manually handled around with ease. With these Factors there would more people being attended to at a time and can be moved to deprived and remote areas.

CHAPTER 3

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This chapter presents the project material selection process and methods. In designing acetate gel electrophoresis for blood protein tests, an identification of specific requirements and design considerations were made for the problems involved. The construction and testing of the developed project were successfully made as shown below.

3.1 PROJECT MATERIALS

Table 3.1 Materials selected for the project were selected based on availability, easiness of integration, development resources and cost. It was designed to minimize cost, without compromising on the functionality of the system. Below is the list of main components for the study

S/no	Material	Specification	Quantity
1	capacitors	47uf/50v	5
2	transformer	220-12v	1
3	Connecting wires	-----	As required
4	Resistors	1k, 3.3k,4k,10k	8/4/7
5	LED	3mm	1

6	Connectors	phono	2
7	12v batteries	_____	1
8	IC	SC3524	1
10	Zero PCB board	_____	1
11	Diode	In4007	4

Table 3.1 main components

3.2 METHODOLOGY

Fig 3.2.1a Initial Design prototype first powered by a 9volt battery to obtain the desired output before the actual construction was made. It was furthered on a PCB.

Fig 3.2.1a Battery connection test

With the wire cutters, cut out two equal pieces of the stainless-steel wire. Both of these pieces should be about 2 cm longer than the width of your rectangular, plastic box. Bend the extra 2 cm of wire into a hook. This will allow the wire to hook over the side of the chamber. This box will serve as the gel chamber. The wires need to be longer than the width of the gel chamber so they can still span across its width after the next step has been completed. Bend the extra 2 cm of wire into a hook. This will allow the wire to hook over the side of the chamber. Place one wire on one end of the chamber, and the second wire at the other end.

Assemble the 15Volt Battery. An inverter is used here to convert the dc to mains voltage. Combing is done by the use of the comb. The comb will need to be wider at the top so it can rest on the edges

of the chamber. Slits can be cut into the outer edges of the comb. This will allow it to stay upright easier. The bottom of the comb needs to have three teeth for each color of food dye. Each tooth should not be touching the bottom of the gel chamber. There needs to be around 1/2 cm of clearance between the bottom of the teeth and the chamber. The teeth also need to be evenly spaced away from each other.

Preparation of buffer as gel. Next with the metal electrodes out of the plastic gel chamber, place the comb into the gel chamber. The comb should be about 1/2 cm from one of the ends of the gel chamber. This 1/2 cm will provide room for you to cut a line in the gel in a later step with a butter knife. Gently pour the rest of the electrolyte over the buffer solution in the chamber. The solution should completely cover and submerge the buffer. Next, firmly grab onto the top of the gel comb and carefully pull it straight up and out of the gel. Be extra careful with this step. The wells formed by the comb in the gel will hold the stains or dyes for this experiment. You will need to make room for the wire electrodes. Take a butter knife and cut 2 lines across the width of the chamber on both ends. You can cut all the way down to the bottom of the chamber. Then, place the wire electrodes back in the chamber. The electrodes should have the same placement as before. It is highly important the entire length of the electrodes are under the surface of the buffer solution. The hook of the electrode does not have to be submerged though. One at a time, each of the three different colors of food coloring will need to be placed in its own well with the syringe. Only a couple drops of each dye are needed. Place one clip of one of the alligator leads on the exposed positive battery terminal. Place the other end of this same lead onto the positive electrode. The positive electrode should be the wire farthest away from the wells. Now, take the other alligator clip lead; one of its clips should be clipped onto the exposed negative battery terminal. Place the other end of this same lead onto the negative electrode. The negative electrode should be the wire closest to the wells. At this point, you should be seeing bubbles bubbling up from the electrodes in the buffer solution because the current is passing through them. Check battery if no bubbles is seen the food coloring will migrate from the side of the chamber with the negative electrode to the end with the positive electrode. Keep running the gel until food coloring bands have clearly and distinctly separated away from each other. While this process is occurring, be sure to check it at least every 5 to 10 minutes. This whole process usually takes around 15 to 30 minutes. The secondary color of food dye separated into different colored bands after the gel electrophoresis ran. This is because the secondary-colored dye contained

different sized macromolecules within it. Different sized molecules will separate at different speeds, resulting in bands at certain locations down the length of the gel

3.3 Block diagram

Fig 3.3.1a system block diagram

The main aim of this project is to design hematological electrophoresis device. Below indicates the diagram that depicts engineering behind the system.

Chargeable batteries are also widely used in inverters, where its DC voltage is converted into mains AC voltage and is used to power the household appliances during mains power failure.

A battery charger is basically a dc power supply source. Here a transformer is used to step down the AC mains input voltage to the required level as per the rating of the transformer.

This transformer is always a high-power type and is able to produce a high current output as required by most lead-acid batteries.

A bridge rectifier configuration is used to rectify the low voltage AC into DC and is further smoothed by a high value electrolytic capacitor.

This DC is fed to an electronic circuit which regulates the voltage into a constant level and is applied to the battery under charge, where the energy is stored through an internal process of chemical reaction.

In automatic battery chargers a voltage sensor circuit is incorporated to sense the voltage of the battery under charge. The charger is automatically switched OFF when the battery voltage reaches the required optimum level.

The capacitors are used in filtering the smoothen current by the full wave rectifier. Zenor diode breaks currents the transistor regulates currents reaching the LED diode.

3.4 Circuit Diagram

Fig 3.4.1a Circuit diagram for hematological electrophoresis

Working principle of the circuit

First diagram

Rectification from AC to DC

1. The Transformer is used to step the AC mains voltage down to 15V.
2. The Bridge rectifier (IN4007) is converting (rectifier) AC 15V to DC
3. The capacitor C1 is filtering or smoothening the AC components in the DC from the rectifier
4. The resistor and R1 and zener diode ZD is regulating the voltage from the smoothing capacitor C₁ and ensuring that the voltage (12V) is constant under all load conditions.
5. R2 and the LED there to indicate that there is power on.
6. The signal diode before the battery is ensuring that there is reverse current from the battery.
7. The transistor is used for switching when the zener voltage is reached,

INVERTER DC-AC

1. There are basically two blocks, thus Driver stage and Power stage.
2. The Driver stage has the SC3524 IC as its active component. The IC has two outputs that come alternatively.
3. The outputs are used to drive two set of Darlington pair transistors that provide a path for current flow in the two primary coils of the transformer in the power stage.
4. The driver stage is only responsible for switching of the two outputs of SC3524 at the desired frequency.

5. when the first output is on the second is off by which time one set of the coils of the transformer will conduct in one direction. At another instance the second output come on and the first goes off by which the other set of coils will conduct in the opposite direction.
6. The output winding, or coil of the transformer will experience alternating current despite the input to the primary coils in the DC.

3.5 flow chart

3.5.1 Start: Start the device by turning ON the power button.

3.5.2 Get the input signal from the mains: the step-down transformer steps down the current from the source.

3.5.3 Rectification: rectifier converts the alternating current to direct current

3.5.4 1st signal: the direct current activates the circuit.

3.5.5 2nd signal: the AC signal deactivates the circuit.

3.5.6 Deactivate the circuit: when rectification stops or no direct current flowing the circuit stops

CHAPTER 4

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The results of the project are presented and discussed in the ensuing sections. Results of the PCB connections, and biomedical optimization and investigative tests are discussed.

Fig 4.1 battery connection

fig 4.2 PCB connection

Fig 4.3 Formica casing

Fig 4.5 Battery power check

4.4 Discussion

The circuit was first designed on a fig 4.5 to check the desired output using a 9volt power supply. After the connections of the components on PCB, a laboratory test was done and the circuit was working properly.

A DC power source is integrated to provide current to drive the blood samples from one terminal to the other to cause band division. The acetate paper gives clearer bands for visible and easy identification. The band divisions are read against a reading hemoglobin chart consisting of various types of hemoglobin Hb A, F, S and C. The divided fragments are read against the chart and patients are diagnosed accordingly. Each hemoglobin component has their own characteristics.

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Conclusion

The main goal of the project is to rapid blood evaluation test machine with less dependence on electricity and also help abolish some superstitious beliefs in the society by designing an

hematological electrophoresis machine. This was made possible by incorporating rechargeable battery and a transformer to serve as alternate power source to the device. The presence of each and every module was reasoned out and placed very carefully. The transformer steps down heavy alternating current from the main and the rectifier converts it to direct current. The battery stores power to be used later by the help of the capacitors. The tray is loaded with blood samples and turned on. With the principle of electrophoresis, the samples are made to pass through charged ions of TDA and they are separated into different fragment by molecular sizes. Readings are then taken for chart assessing and diagnosing.

5.2 Limitations

The hematological electrophoresis device is to be used in almost every place and location and battery drain is a constant problem as batteries needed to be charged every now and then. Overlapping is also a issue due to the coloring and non-controlling ability of the spreading fragments which made reading very difficult sometimes.

5.3 Recommendation

The hematological electrophoresis device can be used by all persons that wishes to know their blood groups and their compatibility of their partners.

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